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A Nanocomposites-based, All-inkjet-printed, Flexible, Ultra-broadband Film Sensor for *in-situ* Acquisition of Dynamic Strain

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OUTLINE

1. Research Motivations & Objectives
2. State of the Art
3. Inkjet-printed Nanocomposite-based Sensors:
 - 3.1 Fabrication Process
 - 3.2 Fundamental Characterization
4. Experimental Results
5. Concluding Remarks

Research Motivation

Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) Solution: **Sensor Network**

- **Spatially Configured** Sensors
- Compromise between **Sensing Effectiveness** and **Sensing Cost**

To Introduce '**Nervous System**' into Engineering Structure

Research Motivation

Sensors: Traditional Methods

- Metal-foil Strain Gauge: Gauge Factor 1-5, Low Frequency, Orientational
- Piezoelectric Transducer: Gauge Factor 50-100, High Frequency, Heavy and Brittle

Metal-foil Strain Gauge

Piezoelectric Transducer

Piezoelectric Wafer

Main Challenge for Sensor Network: **Low Density, Flexibility, Environmental Adaptation**

State of The Art

Solution: **New Materials with New Sensing Mechanism**

- Connection and disconnection of **nanofiller networks** will induce **contact resistance change**.
- The variation of **adjacent nanoparticles distance** will induce **tunneling resistance change**.

$$R = R_{particle} + R_{contact} + R_{tunnel}$$

Region of variation

$$R_{tunnel} = \frac{V}{AJ} = \frac{h^2 d}{Ae^2 \sqrt{2m\lambda}} \exp\left(-\frac{4\pi d}{h} \sqrt{2m\lambda}\right)$$

State of The Art

For Structural Health Monitoring:

- Precise Detection of Micro Cracks
- Quantitive Damage Evaluation

Guided Ultrasonic Wave for Active SHM

Guided Ultrasonic Wave

Characteristics of Guided Ultrasonic Wave:

1. High frequency
2. Ultralow Magnitude

Sensors for Ultrasonic Waves are Needed!

Bottleneck: Most of the Existing Sensors Cannot Reach High Frequency

State of The Art

Manufacturing Process: **Inkjet Printing**

- **Drop-on-Demand, Mask-Less**
- **Simplified Process** (Computer-Aided Design)
- **Direct Deposition** on Flexible or Rigid Substrate
- High Resolution, **High Precision** (tens of micrometres)
- **Mass Production**

Materials Printer
Fujifilm DMP-2830

Materials Cartridges
Fujifilm DMC-11610

Research Objectives

- To develop **nanocomposite-based sensors** filled with carbon nanofillers with **high sensitivity, high fidelity** and **low weight**;
- To simplify the manufacture process with **spraying** and **inkjet printing**;
- To use the inkjet printed nanocomposite-based sensor to capture signals from **low frequency dynamic vibration**, through **medium frequency impact**, to **ultrasonic guided waves**;
- To achieve damage localization by setting up a **all inkjet printed nanocomposite sensing network**;
- To further utilize this innovative sensor for **structural health monitoring** and **wearable devices**.

Fabrication Process

* PVP: Polyvinyl Pyrrolidone
SDBS: Sodium Dodecyl Benzene Sulfonate
NMP: N-Methyl Pyrrolidone
PI: Polyimide

Nanofiller

Carbon Black (CABOT Black Pearl 2000)

Polymer, Surfactant in Solution
(PVP, SDBS in NMP*)

Mechanical Stirring

Sonication Bath

Membrane Filtered
(0.45µm) Ink for Printing

Substrate (PI* film)

Substrate Cleaning (O₂ Plasma)

Inkjet Print on Substrate

Sensor Network

Fabrication Process

KEYPOINT: Ink Design

Requirement for Inks:

$$Z = \frac{\gamma \rho d^{1/2}}{\eta}$$

γ : Surface Tension

ρ : Density

η : Dynamic Viscosity

For Parameter Z:

- $1 < Z < 14$: Stable Droplet, **Printable**
- $0 < Z < 1$: Viscosity Dissipation, **No Droplet Ejection**
- $Z > 14$: **Satellite Droplets**

Our Ink: $Z=13$

Fabrication Process

Inkjet Printing

PiXDRO LP50 Inkjet Print System
(Equipped with Fujifilm DMC-11610
Cartridge)

Printing Process

Drop Screenshot Captured by
Stroboscopic Camera

Spherical Droplets with **NO Clog** and **Satellite Drops**: **Printable** and **Stable** Ink

Fundamental Characterization

Flexible Nanocomposite Sensor Fabricated by Inkjet Printing

Fundamental Characterization

Percolation Threshold

The sensitivity will reach **highest** at around the percolation threshold under quasi-static situation.

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 (f - f_c)^t$$

Filler content Critical Value (Percolation threshold)

Conductivity of nanocomposites
Sensors 18 (2018) 1398

Fundamental Characterization

Electrical Conductivity and Thickness

Near the Percolation Threshold

Electrical Conductivity and Thickness of Sensors: Increase with No. of Layers
A Sudden Increase of Conductivity from 12 to 15 Layers

Experimental Results - Low Frequency Vibration

Experiment Set-up (100 Hz - 2 kHz)

Good Repeatability

Experimental Results – High Frequency GUWs

Experimental Results – High Frequency GUWs

Guided Ultrasonic Wave Signal at 175 kHz (Resonance Frequency of PZT Actuator), 15 cm

- High Sensitivity and Fidelity
- High Signal-to-Noise Ratio
- Without Obvious Delay

Experimental Results – High Frequency GUWs

Guided Ultrasonic Wave Signal at 500 kHz, 15 cm

Broad Sensing Frequency Band

Experimental Results – High Frequency GUWs

Comparison with sensors fabricated by other methods

Nanocomposite sensor fabricated by hot pressing

Thickness: $\sim 200 \mu\text{m}$

Connection: Adhesive

Nanocomposite sensor fabricated by spray coating

Thickness: $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$

Connection: Coated

Nanocomposite sensor fabricated by inkjet printing

Thickness: $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$

Connection: Coated, Adhesive

Relative standard deviation
(based on 100 measurements)

Good Stability

Concluding Remarks

- **Drop-on-Demand Fabrication**

Inkjet Printing has advantages of mildness, simplicity, low-cost and large-scale production. Inkjet Printed Sensors could be fabricated into any desired patterns by computer-aided-design.

- **Light-weight and Flexible**

Inkjet Printed Sensors with microscale thickness could be implemented onto various structure surfaces (flat, curve or complex surface) without weight-penalty.

- **Good Stability and Sensitivity**

The Inkjet Printed Sensor shows good ability to perceive stable dynamic signals in a broadband frequency range up to 500 kHz.

Thanks Very Much!